

A Study of the Reaction between Sulphosalicylic Acid and Sodium Molybdate

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A yellow colour is obtained when sulphosalicylic acid solution is added to a solution of sodium molybdate. A study of the *pH* and conductance, based on monovariation and continued variation methods, of the system Na_2MoO_4 -sulphosalicylic acid shows evidence of chelate formation. The stoichiometry of the chelate is 1:1 and its dissociation constant is found to be 5.04×10^{-3} . A reasonable structure has been suggested.

Complex formation in the cases of sulphosalicylate and various metals, already studied¹⁻⁶, has been found to be due to liberation of sulphonic, phenolic, and carboxylic protons. The author has undertaken a study of the *pH* and conductance of the system sulphosalicylic acid—sodium molybdate, using the monovariation and continued variation methods⁹⁻¹⁰. It has been found that a 1:1 chelate is formed. Addition of the ligand solution to the sodium molybdate solution results in the appearance of a yellow colour which is a further proof of chelation. The possibility of using this reaction in the colorimetric estimation of molybdenum is under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. Sodium molybdate on analysis was found to have the formula $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. A Doran type conductivity bridge with a Omega headphone, a WTW oscillator and dip-type conductivity cell was used for measuring conductance. A Beckman *pH*-meter with glass and saturated calomel electrodes was used for measuring *pH*. Double-distilled water was used to prepare the solutions.

Monovariation Method.—To the molybdate solution (5 ml, *M*/10 and *M*/20) different volumes of equimolar ligand solutions were added such that in the resulting solutions the components were in molar ratios of 1 : 0 to 1 : 5. The total volume was kept constant at

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2. Banks and Peterson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 3062; Foley and Anderson, *ibid.*, 1948, **70**, 1195; Agran, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, **8**, 266.
3. Nanda and Aditya, *this Journal*, 1957, **34**, 577.
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5. Banks and Singh, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **81**, 6159.
6. Sudarikov and Bussrov, *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1956, **1**, 2327.
7. Kuan Pan *et al.*, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **4**, Ser II, 1.
8. Turner and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 912.
9. Pande and Nayar, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, **27A**, 284.
10. Job, *Ann. chim.*, 1928, **x**, 9, 113.

30 ml by addition of requisite volumes of water. Fig. 1 and 2 show the variations of pH and conductance with the addition of the ligand solution.

Vol. of ligand (ml).

FIG. 1

Vol. of ligand (ml).

FIG. 2

Continued Variation Method.—A series of solutions was prepared in which the ratios of molybdate to the ligand was varied, but the total molarity of the two was kept constant and their conductances were measured. Fig. 3 shows the results obtained for $M/80$, $M/100$, and $M/120$ solutions where the differences between the observed conductance of each solution and that calculated from the blanks have been plotted against the percentage of the ligand added. In every case a peak was obtained at molar ratio of 1:1, confirming the stoichiometry.

The same method was applied to determine the dissociation constant of the complex, with the only difference that, keeping the molarity of the ligand solution constant ($M/50$), molarities of the molybdate solutions were varied from $M/80$ and $M/100$ to $M/120$ (curves A, B and C in Fig. 4). The dissociation constant, calculated by the method described by Killeffer and Linz¹¹ comes out to be 5.04×10^{-3} .

DISCUSSION

In sodium molybdate, the metal molybdenum has co-ordination number four. The structure of the anion MoO_4^{2-} has been determined to be tetrahedral arrangement of four oxygen atoms occupying the four co-ordination positions about the Mo^{6+} ion¹². In molyb-

11 "Molybdenum Compounds", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1952.

12 Beech, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1943, 11, 214.

denum complexes, the bond formation involves the *d*-orbitals¹³. In a 1:1 complex, one coordinated oxygen has been replaced by one molecule of the ligand minus its two protons, providing one molecule of water.

Fernandes¹⁴ has shown that the reaction between molybdenum oxide and potassium gallate results primarily in the formation of a 1:1 complex having the structure :

This has been further confirmed by Varde and Athavale¹⁵. Extending this argument to the present study, the structure of the sulphosalicylate complex of molybdenum is suggested to be:

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